

Preparation of procedure proposal for the Ethics committee

Clinical signs in laboratory animals

Francisco E. Olucha-Bordonau

UJI

In the objective of advancing in preparing the procedure proposal to meet all requirements according to ethical and deontological rules in each BC and TC. Centralizing all documents in each experimental WP for procedure validation and ethical approval. Along the first semester, all procedures will need to be approved by local committees/Ministry.

One of the most important aspects to address measures is to avoid animal pain and sufferance by providing anesthesia and/or analgesia in specific moments of experimentation

For the PsyCoMed procedures it is recommend to follow the observations of the clinical signs during procedures to assess animal welfare. This paper by the Federation of European Laboratory Animal Science Associations (FELASA) working group provides a list of clinical signs of discomfort in laboratory animals.

That can be obtained from

[The reporting of clinical signs in laboratory animals](#)